

The Porcupine

A porcupine—
thorny,
yet a beauty,
its heart filled
with quiet purity.

Shy, yet fearless,
it wriggles and wobbles,
moving softly,
parting the grass as it goes.

A mosaic of thorns,
a gentle, benign look—
yet a deadly armor
if ever you provoke.

“Hey, you all,”
it seems to say
as it quietly moves along,

Leave me alone,

let me go.

This jungle is yours,
but it also
belongs to me.

Let me have my little joy,
as you have yours
to see.

— Dr. Aditya Bikram Mishra